

REMARKS ON SURKHONDARYO AREAL LINGUISTICS RESEARCH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10972556>

ANNOTATION

This is it in the article dialectology and areal linguistics of the fields in linguistics to be studied, to the fields about studies review given. Also Surhondarya area and dialects to be studied in particular data provided, studies analysis done and relationship expressed and comments held.

Key words: Areal linguistic, Turkish philology, Uzbek dialects, Uzbek-Tajik dialect;

Areal linguistics, in particular areal study of dialects reach and mapping about all in languages weighty affairs done that it is increased our observation can In particular, E.A Makayev, R. Avanasov, N. Tolstoy, V. Zhirmunsky, M. Borodina, N. Gadzhিয়েva, N. Kiseleva, G. Blagova such as of scientists to areal linguistics in his studies about important research done that it is increased our observation can¹

Turkish philology in terms of area as well language research reach regarding affairs dialectology with in dependence done increased Chunonchi, N. Baskakov, M. Sheraliyev, E. Sevortyan, N. Gadzhিয়েva, A. Karahan, E. Agca, N. Merve, A. Yemel, Nadira Turdubai daughter's works in the field done increased important from studies is considered² Uzbek This is also the case in linguistics about series studies done increased dialects mapping according to AKBorovkov, VVReshetovlar this the first research in the field done increased. Linguistic

¹ Makaev E.A. Problemy Indo-European area linguistics. -M . - L., 1964; Avanesov R.I. Vystuplenie podokladam // Voprosy dialektologii tyurkskikh yazykov. - Baku, 1958. - P. 139-141; Tolstoy N.I. O sootnoshenii tsentralnogo i marginalnogo arealov v sovremennoy Slavii // Arealnoe issledovaniya v zhyzkoznanie i etnografii. - L. , 1977. - S.37-56; Zhirmunsky V.M. German dialectology. -M . -L., 1956.-636 p.; Borodina M.A. Predislovie // Narodi i yazyki Sibiri:arealnye issledovaniya. - M., 1978. -S.3-6; Borodina M.A. Problemy linguistic geography. - M. 1966. - S. 220; Gadjieva N.Z. Problemy Turuskoy arealnoy lingvistiki: Sredneaziatskiy areal. - M. 1975. -303s; Desnitskaya A.V. Questions about the subject and methods of regional linguistics // Arealnye issledovaniya v zhyzkoznanii i etnografii. - L., 1977. - S. 22-29. N.B. Kiseleva N.B. Arealnye vzaimosvyazi slavyanskikh zhyzkov Tsentralnoy zony : autoreferat dis kandida filologicheskix nauk : 10.02.03. - Minsk, 2000. - 20 p. G.F. Blagova . Turuskoe sklonenie v arealno - istoricheskom osveshchenii : (Yugo-Vost. region) / G. F. Blagova . - Moscow : Nauka, 1982. - 304 p.

² Baskakov N.A. Arealy i marginalnye zony v razvit turuskikh zhyzkov // Narodi i zhyzki Sibiri: arealnye issledovaniya. - M., 1978; Sheraliev M.M. Azerba j chan dialectologist j asyn scepters . -B aku, 1981; Sevortyan E.V. Assimilation and dissimilation of the soglasnyx v yujnyx turuskikh language // Issledovaniya po sravnitelnoy grammatike turuskikh language. 1. Phonetics. - M., 1955; Gadjieva N.Z. Problemy Turuskoy arealnoy lingvistiki: Sredneaziatskiy areal. - M., 1975.-303p. A. Karahan . Divan ü Lugti ' t - T ü rk ' e g ö re XI . y ü zy ı l Turkey leh ç e knowledge Ankara University / Sosyal Knowledge Institute / Turkey Literature ı Bö l ü m ü / T ü rk Dili and Literature Ana Knowledge Dal ı . Ph.D. , Turkey .2009. 782 p . E. About Turkey of the language historical dialectologist - Harezmi - Alt ı n Army sahas ı na ait Turkish on texts one review Eskişehir Osmangazi University / Social Knowledge Institute / Türk Dili and Literature Ana Bilim Dalı. Doctorate , 2020.298 p. N. Merve . Turkmen dialectologist : Ashgabat city mouth Hacettepe University / Social Knowledge Institute / Çağdaş Turk Polish and Edebiyatları Ana Bilim Dalı, 2020, 121 p. A. Yemel . Turk dialects between translation system . Nine September University / Science Institute / Computer Mühendisliği Ana Bilim Dalı. Ph.D. , 2013, 159 p. Nadira Turdubai girl Dîvânu In Lugâti't-Türk geography of my skin historical and contemporary Turk with their dialects phonetic and semantic in terms of comparison . Yü ksek License , 2017, 150 p .

geography, linguistics of mapping theoretical aspects A. Shermatov, A. Zorayev in his works statement by doing given³ From him next areal research in years according to Q.Muhammadjonov, Y.Ibrohimov, H.Murodova, I.Darveshov, N.Rakhmonov, G.Norova, S.Polatova such as scientists big monographic in the plan studies done increased⁴. Uzbek dialectology his own development during of dialects phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic characteristics, classification, other languages with relatedness issues wide in terms of research did and this affairs today's still modern today research methods based on body linguistics with depends done in the aspect is increasing. That's it with together, of dialects pure specific Features areal mapping, areal zones in the style of research to reach current problem as is putting Because it is big dialects contained of dialects own pagan, territorial differences observed. In particular, only one Surkhandarya Uzbek dialects pinch dialect to the composition If it enters, the area northern in the part deafness dialect priority that our observation can To this reason as while of the population settlement and urbanization in processes integrated in terms of snow dialect representatives that's it in the regions to live will be Also Persian - Tajik languages with diary connection during this condition developed observation can

Surkhandarya oasis his own dialectal in terms of diversity and pinch dialect the most a lot save the rest area as well as separate study. Demand does Area mapping and linguistic studies to the analysis from entering before, Surkhandarya Uzbek dialects classification, scientific to be studied and Uzbek-Tajik dialects relationship in the matter of affairs to the analysis attention looking at let's go to the goal We consider it appropriate. After all, "Uzbek of the language Surkhandarya region in the territory Uzbek speaker population in his speech a lot century historical development, material and cultural life reflection bringer very a lot and colorful language the facts save it, that's why for this dialects are also different bilaterally historical-descriptive and linguogeographical in aspect to be studied must"⁵.

Surkhandarya oasis dialects research to do about Y.D.Polivanov, A.K.Borovkov, V.V.Reshetov, Gozi Yunusov, Sh.Shoabdurahmanov, A.Mamatkulov, S.Rahimov, Kh.Alimurodov such as of scientists service big it has been⁶. In these works Surkhandarya Uzbek dialects

³ Shermatov A. What is linguistic geography ? - Tashkent : Science, 1981. -B.10; Djuraev A.B. Teoreticheskie osnovy arealnogo issledovaniya Uzbekoyazychnogo massiv. - Tashkent: Science, 1991. -273p.

⁴Mukhamedjanov K. Arealnoe issledovanie uzbekskikh govorov Yuzhnogo Kazakhstan. Autoref .d is ... dra filol.nauk . - Tashkent, 1988. - 44 p.; Djuraev A.B. Teoreticheskie osnovy arealnogo issledovaniya Uzbekoyazychnogo massiv. - Tashkent: Science, 1991; Y. Ibrahimov . South Islander Uzbek dialects research i . Philol . science d - ri ... diss . -T., 2000; Muradova N. Uzbek language Navoi province dialects linguoreal interpretation Philol . science d - ri ... diss . - Tashkent , 2006. - B.309. Darvishov I. South-western Namangan dialects are phonetic and phonological areal research of its characteristics : philology. sciences fals.d-ri (PhD) ... diss. author ref . - F., 2018. - 21 p. Rakhmanov N.S. Uzbek language Navoi province dialects morphological characteristics linguoreal research , Philol . science fake Dr. (PhD) ... diss . - S., 2019. - 139 p. Norova G.M. Uzbek language Zarafshan oasis Uzbek dialects of the lexicon linguoreal research , Philol . science fake Dr. (PhD) ... diss . - Jizzakh , 2021. Polatova SM Vobkent district of the dialect areological research , Doctor of Philology (PhD) ... diss. - Bukhara , 2023.

⁵ Rahimov S. Uzbek language Surkhandarya dialects (phonetics , vocabulary). - Tashkent: Science, 1985, -B. 4

⁶Polivanov E. D. Uzbek dialectology and Uzbek literary language. - Tashkent , 1933. Borovkov A.K. Uzbek -Tajik dvuyazychie i vopros vzaimootnosheniya Tajik-Uzbek language. Uchenye zapiski instituta Vostokovedeniya AN USSR, T. IV. - M., 1952; Borovkov A. K. Voprosy klassifikatsii uzbekskiykh narodnykh govorov. Izvestia AN UzSSR . No. 5. - Tashkent, 1953. Shoabdurahmanov Sh. Uzbek dialectology . - Tashkent , 1978; Reshetov V. V. Uzbek language, ch.1. Phonetics. - Tashkent, 1959; Reshetov V. V. Question transcript. Uchenye zapiski TGPI im. Nizami vvp . 1. - Tashkent, 1947; Reshetov V. V. About the dialectal basis of the Uzbek literary language . j . "Voprosy

grouping, lexical-morphological level around research done without considerations held. Surkhandarya Uzbek Uzbek of the population language whole one whole dialect organize not enough, different of dialects territorial or mixed in case to meet remarks it is dialectologist scientist S. Rahimov them as follows classification does:

- 1) J is the recipient Uzbek dialects (Kipchak to the dialect special dialects);
- 2) Y is the recipient Uzbek dialects (Karluk to the dialect special dialects);
- 3) Two in the language speaker dialects ⁷.

We research doing Eastern Surkhandarya Uzbek-Tajik dialects the third to the group our input can Because it is in the regions I don't know very strong observed. In the area from time immemorial Uzbeks with one in line Tajiks also live side by side came Two the nation representatives to live condition, life, economy activity, culture mutually is common. Tajik and Uzbek peoples between such closeness from the sixth century AD started⁸ This closeness is centuries old even in development in terms of developed. In the XVIII-XIX centuries this area from time to time with Bukhara khanate to the composition entered Bukhara of the khanate socio-economic conditions at the beginning of the 20th century come in it living of nations national merger of processes complete that it is not set gave This is the whole situation khanate, that's it including the northern one Surkhandarya, Tajikistan ethnic of the composition extremely in diversity manifestation it has been. Tajikistan and Surkhan oasis ethnographic situation learned historian BXKarmysheva this of the area ethnic composition about information will give since, in the area Tajiks and from Uzbeks except less numerous Turkmens, Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Karakalpaks, Arabs, Gypsies, Indian, Khazars, Baluchis and come output complete sure didn't happen small groups (chinaki, larkhobi, shoumari, sudjoni) lived. sudjony, utabuloki, obsarina, kavoli) are also residences to do and area of the Tajiks themselves language, material and spiritual culture in terms of from each other a little difference who does two big to the group that is divided, this from groups one Chagatai (in the region all to 20.6% of Tajiks close), the second while conditional respectively Kulobi (about 75%) is called about stopping passes ⁹.

Surkhandarya area in dialects two in the language spoken (bilingualism) dialects there is being, this of dialects appear to be main reason as centuries during formed trade-economic, political, cultural closeness and one how many centuries during whole statehood in the system that they lived to bring can Surkhandarya Boysun-Shorchi group dialects research reached linguist Kh. Fayziyeva exactly that to the group incoming in the regions bilingualism dialects priority being Tajik - Uzbek of languages historical roots M. Koshgari, A. Navoi that it is also expressed in his works emphasized without, Boysun-Shorchi in the group Uzbek-Tajik dialects below differences cause passes:

1. In dialect sonar from the consonant after came Ch sonorous sound j such as pronunciation will be: t:nch – tinž, peace – ti:nžlik, angle – büržäk, triangle – üčbüržäk such as.

yazikoznaniya " No. 1. 1955. Gozi Olim Yunusov Uzbek dialects from the classification one experience (lat in the alphabet). - Tashkent , 1936. Shoabdurahmanov Sh. Uzbek literary language and Uzbek people dialects . - Tashkent , 1962; Shoabdurahmanov Sh. Base sha har dialects from the lexicon . UzDM , 11. - Tashkent , 1960. Mamatkulov A. Sherabad district manager dialect Philol . science name diss . - Tashkent , 1960. Rahimov S. Surkhandarya in the area Uzbek dialects lexicon : Philol . science name diss . - Tashkent , 1974. Alimurodov Kh. Lower Surkhandarya Uzbek pinch dialects morphology . Philol . science name diss . - Tashkent , 1982.

⁷ Rahimov S. Uzbek language Surkhandarya dialects (phonetics , vocabulary). - Tashkent : Science , 1985, -B. 13.

⁸ Gafurov B.G. History of the Tajik nation. -M . 1952. -B.110

⁹ Karmysheva B. X. K istorii formirovaniya naseleniya ujuynkh rayonov Uzbekistana i Tadjikistana. Soviet ethnography. -M.: 1964, -C.98.

2. x phoneme - fricative, sonorous, deep language back consonant of words all in joints occurs: xāl, khel, xeš-tabar, mexča, mex, gulmex such as.

3. he, this, this pronouns with formed there, that's it on the ground, this on the ground such as ravishes orga, šergä, bergä in the style of it is said.

4. Of the speaker said opinion or of action to be fulfilled has been confidence denotative modal words: definitely - älvättä, undoubtedly - bešüpha; guess Denoting modal words: perhaps - je:ti:mal, apti:d ä n, mabādā, mägäräm such as pronunciation will be done¹⁰. We also understand from these examples maybe, though one language his family organize if not, Tajik-Uzbek language mutually common in touch developed, this areal linguistics of the regions features sure marking, mapping relevance occupation is enough

Tajik in the language dialects their territorial features about studies have also passed since the 60s of the century wide learn started In these studies Uzbekistan in the area Tajik dialects language features research reached things are the same how much organize is enough In particular, Urgut, Shahrisabz, Forish, Kitab, Andijan, Chirchik in the regions living Tajik dialects L. Nazarova, B. Sadullayev, V. Kasimov, M. Mahmudov, J. Murvatov, M. Kabirovlar by dialectal research done¹¹ This research in their work social of the lexicon area in dialects express issues stopping passed without, they linguo-geographical method to maps not downloaded. In particular, L. Nazarova's "Urgut Tajik Dialects research is also the area of the dialect phonetics, morphology, syntax, lexicon to research dedicated.

The theoretical research of areal linguistics in Uzbek linguistics began in the 80s of the 20th century in parallel with direct dialectological research. In this regard, Aziz Jorayev's candidacy on the topic "Areal study of the morphology of the Upper Kashkadarya Uzbek dialects" and doctoral thesis entitled "Theoretical foundations of the areal study of the Uzbek language" laid the groundwork for important research on the relevance and prospects of this field. The scientist's monograph entitled "Theoretical foundations of the areal study of the Uzbek-speaking region" ¹²served as an important source for the areal study of the Turkic and Uzbek-speaking region. In the parts of this monograph entitled "Turkic languages as some methodological issues of areal linguistics", "Reflection", "as the main factor of the formation and development of linguo-areal studies in Uzbek linguistics", the relevant issues of the field are analyzed. It is known that reflection means regrouping and analyzing and evaluating data to achieve new goals along with the achievements obtained as a result of empirical (cognitive, descriptive) study of Uzbek dialects and written monuments. Therefore, A. Jorayev's research is aimed at re-evaluating and analyzing the data obtained as a result of the local regional

¹⁰ Fayziyeva X. Ch . Uzbek language Boysun is a poet group dialects dictionary features . Doctor of Philology (PhD) ... diss. author - Termiz , 2023. -B.17

¹¹ L.R. Nazarova . Govory tadjhikov Urguta: dissertation... kandida filologicheskix nauk: 10.00.00. - Samarkand, 1971. - 359 p.; B. Sadullaev . Govory tadjhikov Shakhriyabza . Abstract dis . na soiskanie uchenoy stepi kandida filologicheskix nauk. (661) / AN Tajik SSR . Otd-nie obshchestv . n auk. – Dushanbe: 1972. - 29 p. V. Kasimov . Govory tadjhikov Forisha . Abstract dis . na soiskanie uchenoy stepeni kandida filologicheskix nauk / Tadj . Mr. un-t im. V. I. Lenina. - Monday: 1966. - 28 p.

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¹² Djuraev A.B. Teoreticheskie osnovy arealnogo issledovaniya Uzbekoyazychnogo massiv. - Tashkent: Science, 1991. - 219 B.

description of Uzbek dialects in the 30s-80s of the 20th century from the point of view of the areal research method ¹³.

In general, areal research is developing rapidly today. However, there are some problems related to the creation of linguistic maps and atlases in the field, which indicates that the research in this direction has not yet been completed. Some of the languages and linguo-areal studies dedicated to this field that we consider relevant can

¹³ Murodova N. Uzbek dialectology. Textbook. - Tashkent, 2019. - p.125 .

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